

Experimental analysis of a perforated-rib-type shear connector with circular holes and centered rebar under static and cyclic loading

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ABSTRACT

The Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite-Plate (SCSC-Plate), which was devised as a new type of deck slab for railway bridges as a more economical alternative to full-section steel plates, is currently being developed at TU Wien. This type of slab utilizes steel plates with circular holes as shear connectors to enable the transfer of shear forces between the external steel chord plates through a concrete core. The load-bearing mechanisms of the SCSC-Plate can be differentiated into a primary direction parallel to the shear connector ribs, where the shear transfer via the shear connectors plays an essential role, and a secondary direction perpendicular to the shear connectors. Previously published research (1-4) has focused on the primary load-bearing direction and the load transfer via the shear connectors without any rebar.

Current research focuses on the perforated-rib-type shear connector with an added centered rebar. One objective is to obtain parameters describing the mechanical properties of a reinforced shear connector and to analyze the influence of cyclic loading on these mechanical properties. Therefore, a test series is being conducted using fiber optic measurements in the surrounding concrete and on the surface of the rebar to seek detailed insight into the shear connectors' response to the specified loading conditions. The test series uses a push-out configuration of a single shear connector with varying load levels.

This contribution provides an overview of the load-bearing mechanisms in the SCSC-Plate and the development of the described test series and test setup. In addition, the research questions addressed with these particular test specimens are presented.

Keywords: Bridge Structures, Composite Steel Structures, Fatigue & Fracture

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

With an increasing number of existing railway bridges reaching the end of their lifespan, either refurbishment or replacement of these structures is necessary. At the time of these bridges' initial construction, an open deck (without a ballast bed) was a prevalent choice, resulting in a low overall depth of the bridge deck but failing to meet today's standards in noise reduction, maintenance requirements, and passenger comfort. (5)

To fulfill today's requirements of the Austrian Federal Railways (ÖBB), a ballasted deck is recommended and needs to be considered when designing a replacement build. The clearance underneath the bridge usually remains fixed, and elevating the rail top level would result in a change of the rail line gradient over a significant section of the railway track, thus being economically unviable, especially for short-span bridges. These geometrical constraints resulting from the existing railway tracks often require a structure with a shallow cross-sectional depth.

1.2 Proposed Solution

One solution to the problem, which is available for both plate and trough bridges, is a heavy steel plate, e.g., 120 mm thick - depending on the span of the bridge. While satisfying the requirement for minimal cross-sectional depth, this proposal exhibits drawbacks such as limited availability of steel plates of this thickness, problematic weldability in trough bridge applications, and inefficient utilization of steel at the mid-plane of the steel plates.

As an alternative solution, the Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite-Plate (SCSC-Plate) is proposed by the Institute of Structural Engineering, Research Department Steel Structures at the TU Wien. With a cross-sectional depth of 200 mm in its current development stage, the SCSC-Plate represents a composite cross-section addressing the previously mentioned issues. *Fig. 1* shows the case, where the SCSC-Plate represents the primary load-bearing element of a slab bridge.

Fig. 1. SCSC-Plate used as a slab bridge a) Longitudinal-section und b) Cross-section (all dimensions in mm).

The SCSC-Plate consists of two outer steel chords with a thickness of 15 mm, shear connectors with circular holes (perforated strips (6)), and primary and secondary reinforcement. Due to the lack of accessibility of the weld interfaces, the concrete interacts with the alternately welded shear connectors to ensure the shear connection of the chord plates.

The manufacturing process is shown in *Fig. 2*. In the first step, two partial cross-sections are created by welding the perforated strips to each of the outer chords with a spacing of 880 mm, using a fillet weld. Subsequently, the two partial cross-sections are stacked together, and the shear connectors intertwine in a comb-like manner, resulting in a spacing of 440 mm of the alternately welded shear connectors. Either before or after assembling the partial cross-sections, secondary reinforcement (stirrups) can be installed, while the primary reinforcement, which runs through the circular holes, is always installed after the assembly of the complete mild steel cross-section. After this pre-manufacturing process, the concrete is cast.

Fig. 2. The assembly process of the SCSC-Plate (all dimensions in mm).

The SCSC-Plate can be used for trough bridges and slab bridges, as shown in *Fig. 1*, where the SCSC-Plate represents the only load-bearing element. The targeted spans for both scenarios are approximately 4.5 m.

1.3 Research goal

The objective of the research concerning the SCSC-Plate is to implement a design guide for the structure complying with the Eurocodes (7-9), which will enable the application of the SCSC-Plate

as a bridge deck in the future. To achieve this, it is necessary to understand the load transfer mechanisms in the structure. The load-bearing mechanisms of the SCSC-Plate can be differentiated into a primary direction parallel to the shear connector ribs (paSC) and a secondary direction perpendicular to the shear connector ribs (peSC). Bending moments are carried in both directions via the two outer chord plates. The shear force in the direction paSC is transferred via the fillet welds, the shear connectors, and concrete struts formed between two adjacent shear connectors. In the other direction (peSC), shear is transferred in the concrete core via two different mechanisms depending on the welding configuration of the adjacent shear connectors and the direction of the shear transfer. This paper focuses on investigating the primary load-bearing mechanism, especially in the local load transfer zone, where concrete, reinforcement, and shear connector ribs interact. The test specimen used in the experimental tests and described in *Section 2* represents one single shear connector. Previous research on these shear connectors was carried out by Palotas (4). In his research, he focused on an unreinforced shear connector under expected loads for the use case slab bridge to gain insight into the stiffness and its time dependency. Based on this research, the test specimen was further developed and equipped with a primary reinforcement according to the current configuration of the SCSC-Plate and fiber optic sensors.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

To investigate the mechanical behavior of a perforated-rib-type shear connector with circular holes and centered rebar, 18 push-out specimens were designed and fabricated as shown in *Fig. 3a*. These test specimens represent the use case of a slab bridge.

A single shear connector (see *Fig 3b*), with a web thickness of 20 mm and a hole diameter of 100 mm, was embedded in concrete. The load was applied via an end plate welded to the shear connector. To resemble the load-bearing mechanism in the SCSC-Plate, three edge surfaces had to be restricted from transferring any load. On the lateral surfaces of the rib a Teflon layer was applied to reduce any occurring friction. Direct load transfer from the rib to the bottom plate via the concrete below the shear connector was prevented by using a polystyrene volume below the rib itself (see *Fig 3a*). The segment of steel box section surrounding the concrete worked both as formwork and as an outer reinforcement to prevent premature splitting failure by providing some confinement for the concrete.

The materials were chosen according to the current preliminary configuration of the SCSC-Plate. All steel elements are of steel grade S355 with a characteristic yield stress of 355 N/mm², and the reinforcement is of grade B550 with a characteristic yield stress of 550 N/mm². The concrete is of strength class C40/50 with a characteristic compressive strength of 40 N/mm².

Fig. 3a and *Fig. 3c* show the test setup and the location of the LVDTs. The test specimen was further equipped with four fiber optic sensors to measure internal strains inside the specimen. The fiber optic measurement system used was Luna Odisi-6104 by Luna Innovations Incorporated. Two fiber optic sensor cables, armored with a central metal tube and a structured polyamide outer sheath, were directly embedded in the concrete. As shown in blue in *Fig. 3a*, these sensors were placed in the concrete on the top and bottom of the shear connector to gain knowledge about possible crack formation occurring during the test.

Another two fiber optic sensing cables with a chemically bonded polyimide coating were directly applied to the surface of the reinforcement bar in a notch next to a longitudinal ridge (depicted in yellow *Fig. 3a*). Before applying the sensors, any surface rust was mechanically removed, and the notch surface was cleaned to remove any residual dust and grease. After cleaning, the sensor cable was applied using an ethyl-cyanoacrylate-based glue. The sensors were covered with a paraffin layer to protect the fiber itself and to limit the measured strain to the elongation of the reinforcement only. These sensors were placed on the top and the bottom of the rebar to account for expected bending effects in the rebar.

The fiber optic sensors enable a distributed measurement of strains in both rebar and concrete. Sensors directly applied to the rebar provide precise strain measurements due to the high sensitivity of

polyimide-coated sensors. Meanwhile, sensors embedded within the concrete are less sensitive, as the strains are somewhat smeared due to the construction of the sensors. They do not capture precise strain peaks in the concrete but can be used for observing crack formation and determining crack width when the occurring strain is integrated, which needs to be considered when working with the data. (10)

Fig. 3. Test Specimen a) Layout of the assembled specimen with the implemented measurement technique b) Layout of Shear Connector with end plate c) test setup (all dimensions in mm).

The static tests were conducted according to EN 1994 (9), which is further explained in Section 3.3. For the dynamic tests, the specimens were subjected to 2 million load cycles with a loading frequency of 5 Hz. Throughout one test, the upper and lower load levels were kept constant. For the cyclic tests,

the lower load level was set at $P_{\min} = 10$ kN, whereas the upper load levels, denoted as P_{\max} , were determined according to *Table 1*. This results in load ranges spanning from $\Delta P = 65$ kN to 190 kN. Before the cyclic loading with a frequency of 5 Hz., the initial loading and slower load cycles were conducted to measure the initial strains occurring in the reinforcement and to obtain data on the stiffness of the reinforced shear connector.

Following the cyclic loading, additional slow load cycles were applied to certain test specimens to understand the impact of cyclic loading on the shear connector's stiffness. They were followed by a static test aimed at measuring the ultimate shear capacity of the specimens.

Additionally, two test specimens (S11, S14, see *Table 1*) were disassembled immediately after the last slow load cycles to rule out possible fatigue failure of the reinforcement and examine the concrete's state in the load transfer area. No damage resulting from the applied load could be observed.

Table 1. Test Regime

Static Tests							
S01							
S02							Conducted according to EN 1994
S03							
Cyclic Tests		P_{\min}	P_{\max}	ΔP	$\Delta P / \Delta P_{Ed}=50\text{kN}$	f	number of cycles
		[kN]	[kN]	[kN]	[%]	[Hz]	[-]
S04	load levels to determine a "safe" cyclic shear force per shear connector	10	110	100	200%	5	2.00E+06
S05		10	120	110	220%	5	2.00E+06
S06		10	130	120	240%	5	2.00E+06
S07		10	140	130	260%	5	2.00E+06
S08		10	150	140	280%	5	2.00E+06
S09		10	160	150	300%	5	2.00E+06
S10		10	170	160	320%	5	2.00E+06
S11		10	170	160	320%	5	2.00E+06
S12		10	180	170	340%	5	2.00E+06
S13		10	190	180	360%	5	2.00E+06
S14	10	200	190	380%	5	2.00E+06	
S15	Serviceability load levels	10	95	85	170%	5	2.00E+06
S16		10	75	65	130%	5	2.00E+06
S17		10	95	85	170%	5	2.00E+06
S18		10	75	65	130%	5	2.00E+06

3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

A central goal of this testing campaign is to obtain data for the validation of FE models - either a model of the test specimen itself or larger models of a bridge - and for the development of various engineering models, which will be derived from both experimental and numerical data and later used for multiple code checks in the designing process of a structure with SCSC-Plate.

This chapter provides an overview of the research questions, which the tests are designed to help answer. Furthermore, a selection of the results of specimen S12, which was loaded cyclically with $\Delta P = 170$ kN ($P_{\max} = 180$ kN), is presented. The specimen was chosen based on the quality and availability of the fiber optic sensor data; in this case, there was insignificant noise and no other malfunction of the fiber optic sensors.

3.1 What is a safe cyclic shear force?

A comprehensive study on the fatigue behavior of the shear connectors, specifically the steel part, was conducted by Takács using the local strain-life method (3, 11) and was confirmed with cyclic push-out tests (12). The experimental campaign described in this paper focuses on the fatigue behavior of the concrete and reinforcement and has the objective to find a safe cyclic shear force that can be endured 2 million times without failure of the test specimen.

Failure of the specimen was defined in analogy to the definition of fatigue failure of the concrete itself, where three stages can be considered (see Fig. 4a). Stage I shows a decelerating increase of the strains with increasing load cycle count. Stage II is characterized by a constant increase of the strains and a decrease of the modulus of deformation. This is followed by Stage III, showing a rapidly accelerating growth of the strains, ultimately resulting in the failure of the concrete. (13-15)

The focus is on evaluating the fatigue behavior of the described test specimens instead of the material itself. As the strains could not be measured and used as an assessment criterion for failure, the relative displacement between the shear connector and the concrete was measured, assuming that a deterioration of the reinforced concrete surrounding the shear connector is responsible for this displacement.

Eleven specimens (S04-S14) were subjected to 2 million load cycles, where the load range was kept constant throughout each test. With every consecutive test, the upper load was increased by 10 kN up, starting from 110 kN for specimen S04. Since the critical cyclic shear force was and still remains unknown the objective was to gradually approach the critical load from below and to obtain the confirmation of safe shear forces. A cyclic test was stopped if no failure occurred during the 2 million load cycles.

Fig. 4. Fatigue behavior of concrete a) Three stage fatigue deformation of concrete in general (15)
b) Relative displacement versus load cycles showing failure and no failure over 2 million load cycles

For instance, the initial test involved a load range of 100 kN (S04), followed by eleven additional specimens with progressively higher load ranges, showing no signs of fatigue failure. This approach demonstrated the very high probability of the 100 kN load range being “safe”, as it was specifically tested once and confirmed by ten additional specimens with higher load ranges. This methodology provides a basis for checks, allowing for the selection of a load level considering the number of specimens tested at higher loads as a measure of safety.

One of the tested load ranges was $\Delta P = 170$ kN ($P_{\max} = 180$ kN) on specimen S12, where the relative displacement over the applied load cycles is depicted in Fig. 4b. Throughout the 2 million load cycles, the relative displacement increased by 31%, from $\delta_i = 0.59$ mm to $\delta_{\max} = 0.78$ mm. The load was considered not to have produced a failure, as a rapidly accelerating increase in the displacement could not be observed.

Additionally, *Fig. 4b* depicts the relative displacement over the applied load for three illustrative specimens (dashed lines), showing potential failures and the specimens' behavior when no failure occurs at a higher initial relative displacement δ_i .

The magnitude of the critical shear force and the associated initial displacement δ_i remain unknown. They may be a subject for future research, possibly determined by further increasing the load range ΔP . No failure could be observed within the tested load ranges ΔP (see *Table 1*).

3.2 What is the stiffness of a perfobond shear connector with centered rebar?

The stiffness of the shear connector can be obtained from load-displacement curves from various slow load cycles before and after the cyclic tests as well as from the static tests. The influence of the magnitude of the applied force and the load cycles on the stiffness will be investigated in the future. These stiffness parameters can be used for validating FE models (e.g., small-scale models of the test specimen itself or also large-scale, more complex models of parts of the bridge). Another use case is the application in simplified engineering models for designing SCSC-bridge decks, which may consider only the load-bearing direction parallel to the shear connectors. An approach using the direct stiffness method was presented by Palotas (16, 4) in his spring framework model for an unreinforced configuration of the SCSC-Plate. It could be easily adapted by using the newly determined stiffness parameters.

Specimen S12 was subjected to three slow load cycles for the following load levels each: $P_{30} = 30$ kN, $P_{50} = 50$ kN, $P_{70} = 70$ kN, $P_{90} = 90$ kN, and $P_{110} = 110$ kN. The lower boundary $P_{\min}=10$ kN was kept constant. The initial loading phase, which led to an initial displacement of $\delta_i = 0.38$ mm, is not depicted (see *Fig. 5a*).

Fig. 5. a) Initial load-displacement-curve before cyclic loading with slow load cycles (S12)
b) Strains and stresses in the vicinity of the shear connector measured for concrete and rebar (S12)

For the first two load levels (30 kN, 50 kN), elastic behavior can be observed, and the loading stiffness can be estimated as $k \sim 2400$ kN/mm. For the first load cycle up to 70 kN (3rd load level), a decrease of stiffness when surpassing $P \sim 60$ kN and residual plastic deformation after the unloading process occur. During the remaining two load cycles of the 3rd load level, the loading stiffness is again $k \sim 2400$ kN/mm, and no further plastic deformation occurs. For the following two load levels (90 kN, 110 kN), the same behavior can be observed: the stiffness decreases when surpassing the previously

applied load level, resulting in an additional plastic deformation after the first unloading of each load level. For these load levels, a plastic deformation can also be detected when applying the same load again in the following two load cycles, where the additional deformation occurs when the load is at its peak.

After the initial application of a particular load level, the stiffness of specimen S12 can be approximated as $k \sim 2400 \text{ kN/mm}$.

3.3 What is the ultimate shear capacity of a single shear connector?

The static failure load was determined for specimens that underwent prior cyclic testing in the fatigue test (S04-S11, S12, S13, S15-S18), along with three additional specimens (S01-S03) that were not subjected to cyclic testing before the static test and, therefore, served as a reference.

The static test was conducted according to EN 1994-1-1 (9) Appendix B, but modifications were made for the specimens also used in the fatigue test.

For those, the 25 load cycles before load increase until failure were omitted as 2 million load cycles had already been performed in the fatigue tests, and load cycles with increasing upper load levels were used instead to determine the specimens' stiffness. The chosen load levels for these alternative cycles were $P = 180 \text{ kN}$, 200 kN , 300 kN , 400 kN , and 500 kN (see Fig. 6)

All tested specimens show similar qualitative behavior; for example, specimen S12 is depicted in Fig. 6. The load-displacement curve shows ductile behavior with a relative displacement of $\delta = 2.8 \text{ mm}$ at the peak load of $P_{ult.} = 772.1 \text{ kN}$ and further relative displacement until $\delta = 6.1 \text{ mm}$ when the load decreases to $0.8 \cdot P_{ult.} = 617.7 \text{ kN}$.

Fig. 6. Load-displacement-curve for specimen S12

3.4 Which load transfer mechanisms occur in the vicinity of the shear connector, and is it possible to quantify them using fiber optic measurement?

The fiber optic sensors integrated into the specimen facilitate quasi-continuous strain measurements along the reinforcement and concrete within the targeted region – the vicinity of the shear connector. This allows for the collection of extensive information on the internal behavior of the specimen during load application, especially the longitudinal strains in and around the reinforcement.

In Fig. 5b, the strains and stresses in the area of interest (see Fig. 3a) in both rebar and concrete are depicted for the specified load levels in Fig. 5a ($P_{30} = 30 \text{ kN}$, $P_{50} = 50 \text{ kN}$, $P_{70} = 70 \text{ kN}$, $P_{90} = 90 \text{ kN}$, and $P_{110} = 110 \text{ kN}$). The stresses are calculated using Hooke's law with a Young's modulus of $E_{cm} = 36000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for concrete and $E_{sm} = 200000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the rebar. The Young's modulus of the concrete was tested and interpolated for the specific age of the specimen at the time of testing.

Strains and stresses are depicted for both the reinforcement and the concrete itself in Fig. 5b, where $x=0 \text{ mm}$ is the center of the shear connector. The top two graphs in Fig. 5b show the strains along the top and bottom of the reinforcement. The sensor along the top of the rebar is in compression, with increasing compressive strains for load levels 1, 2, and 3 and decreasing compressive strains for load levels 4 and 5. The sensor along the bottom of the rebar is under tension, with an increase of the strains affine to the increase of plastic deformation of the specimen.

An expected local bending of the rebar (due to dowel action) could not be identified for the investigated load levels. Instead, both compressive and tensile strains are distributed along the rebar and show a jagged shape, even after post-processing the data, which has been filtered using the moving-median method with a window length ($\Delta x = 13$ mm) corresponding to the rib spacing of the rebar ($s = 12$ mm).

Nevertheless, an effect of the dowel action is expected to be observed for higher load levels during the static tests, where data evaluation is still ongoing.

The bottom two graphs in *Fig. 5b* show the strains measured in the concrete near the top and bottom of the shear connector (see *Fig. 3a*). Like the reinforcement, the concrete is under compression at the top and under tension at the bottom of the shear connector. At the top, in the load transfer zone, compressive strains start increasing with the first load level applied. In contrast, at the bottom, the strains only start increasing with the 3rd load level, correlating with the increase of plastic deformation depicted in *Fig. 5a*. The stresses measured are well below the tensile strength of the concrete C40/50 of $f_{ctm} = 3.7$ N/mm², which was measured in the material tests, so it can be assumed that no cracking occurred for the investigated load levels.

These strain measurements aim to improve existing numerical models and derive a relation between the observed strains and the applied load, focusing on the extreme values, the strain range, and the strain distribution along the rebar. The data from the sensors directly embedded in the concrete will be used for crack detection and assessment of whether the numerical models can depict crack formation accordingly.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This paper gives an overview of the research questions trying to be addressed with a push-out test specimen equipped with fiber optic sensors and subjected to different testing programs (cyclic and static loading). Test results are presented and discussed. The obtained data provides a basis for developing design guidelines for the application of reinforced perforated rib-type shear connectors and, more specifically, for further development of a design guideline for using the SCSC-Plate as a bridge deck structure.

The experimentally derived safe cyclic shear force can be used for fatigue design of such shear connectors with reinforcement. The obtained stiffness properties provide a basis for modeling the SCSC-Plate as a whole without considering the detailed geometry of the shear connectors. The measured strains, shear capacity, and stiffness values may be used to validate FE models and their underlying material models.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research project “Development of the SCSC-Plate as a slender deck slab for railway bridges” is facilitated by the Austrian association for construction technology (Österreichische Bautechnik Vereinigung) öbv and funded by 20 individual sponsors:

ÖBB-Infrastruktur AG, MCE GmbH, Strabag AG, Swietelsky AG, Porr AG, Österreichischer Stahlbauverband, Baumann + Obholzer ZT-GmbH, SBV ZT GmbH, Tecton Consult Engineering ZT GmbH, ISP ZT GmbH, Revotec ZT GmbH, Potyka & Partner ZT GmbH, StahlVerbundBau Consulting GmbH, KOB ZT-GmbH, austroSteel Dr. Gerald LUZA, Niehsner GmbH, Doka Österreich GmbH, Franz Oberndorfer GmbH & Co KG, Materialprüfanstalt Hartl GmbH and Dipl.-Ing. Wolfgang Kirchmair, Ingenieurkonsulent.

The authors would like to thank these sponsors for their contributions to this research project.

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